

Climate Change and National Development in Nigeria: An Evaluation of Policy Responses from 2012 to 2022

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria, like many nations, is increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. The 2012 nationwide flooding, which affected 30 of Nigeria's 36 states, marked a turning point in the country's climate discourse, bringing the issue into national focus. This paper explores the intersection of climate change and national development in Nigeria between 2012 and 2022, a decade characterised by heightened climate variability, recurring environmental disasters, and evolving policy responses. Adopting an interdisciplinary approach that draws on environmental history, policy analysis, and socioeconomic data, the study investigates how climate change has affected key sectors such as agriculture, energy, health, and infrastructure. The study identifies 2012 as a pivotal year not only due to the scale of the flooding but also because of growing empirical evidence linking climate change to rising food insecurity, internal displacement, slowed economic growth, and the country's adoption of the National Climate Change Policy (NCCP). The study adopts a qualitative, interpretive methodology grounded in discourse analysis while applying a purposive data sampling method. The study relies on secondary data sources. The Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) was used to analyse how policy responses are shaped within Nigeria's climate agenda. This paper aims to assess Nigeria's climate governance and its broader implications for sustainable national development and thus recommends that the operationalisation of the Climate Change Act empower the National Council on Climate Change to enforce cross-sectoral compliance and also develop concrete localised adaptation models.

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1.1. Introduction

The year 2012 marked a significant chapter in Nigeria's climate change discourse, climate governance and climate policy responses. The unprecedented flood, which affected 30 of the nation's 36 states, brought the realities of changing weather patterns and climate-induced disasters to the forefront of the national consciousness. This catastrophe exposed the country's profound vulnerability and created an urgent need for a structured national response. That same year, the Nigerian government adopted the National Climate Change Policy 2012 (NCCP), a major step in the country's climate governance structure.

This foundational document established a comprehensive framework to address the dual challenges of adaptation and mitigation. Its strategic goals were to integrate climate resilience into the country's national development plans, combat climate impacts like extreme weather and food insecurity, and pursue a low-carbon, high-growth economic pathway. By aligning its national strategy with global climate efforts, the policy document positioned Nigeria to contribute to international cooperation while safeguarding its own future (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2021).

Since the 1990s, climate change has evolved from a scientific challenge into a pressing societal crisis. Hence, this national awakening occurred within the context of the escalating global concern. Globally, climate change is intensifying weather variability, flooding, droughts, heatwaves, and wildfires, and it has also fueled insecurity, displacement, and forced migration. Major scientific bodies, including the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), have consistently highlighted these interconnected threats, defining climate change not merely as an environmental issue but as an existential risk and threat to national development and global stability (IPCC., 2019).

Globally, the impact of climate change has been shown to be largely unequal. Despite contributing the least to global greenhouse gas emissions, developing and least-developed countries, like Nigeria, disproportionately bear the brunt of its impacts. This glaring injustice is not a matter of chance but a consequence of systemic vulnerabilities caused by several factors that include: policy direction, poverty, inadequate financial resources, lack of infrastructure, and ineffective climate governance, characterised by corruption and a lack of proper planning that severely limits these nations' capacity to implement robust adaptation and mitigation strategies. Consequently, they are left with heightened exposure to climate shocks, diminished ability to respond, and a weakened cycle of recovery that stifles sustainable national development (Birkmann, J. et al., 2022).

The disparity in climate vulnerability is evident in many recent studies (Cook, J. et al., 2016; Nura, U., & Grey, A., 2023). According to a 2022 report by the Global Center on Adaptation, it states that that climate change acts as a risk multiplier by amplifying pre-existing vulnerabilities, particularly across Africa. The report illustrates this crisis with devastating clarity; between January 2021 and September 2022 alone, more than 50 million people on the continent had their lives and livelihoods devastated by climate-induced droughts, floods, and other extreme weather events (Global Centre on Adaptation, 2022). This statistic is not merely numbers, but it brings into sharp focus the immediate and escalating human cost of inaction and ineffective policy response. It underscores the existential challenge climate change poses to national development and stability, highlighting the non-negotiable urgency for robust, globally-supported adaptation and mitigation strategies in the world's most vulnerable regions.

Despite the country's active participation in global climate governance since 1992 and a leading voice in climate change matters in Sub-Saharan Africa, the situation in Nigeria is not in any way better. In 1994, Nigeria ratified the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and has since then attended various Conference of the Parties (COPs), ratified various global and regional agreements to cut

carbon emissions, reduce greenhouse gases (GHGs), enhance adaptation and improve mitigation.

Empirical review showed that Nigeria's military-led governments, particularly between 1990, when global attention to climate change began to intensify, and 1999, when democratic governance was restored to the country, gave minimal attention to climate-related challenges. The country's failure to implement substantial national climate policies or institutional responses during the military period, despite the country's active participation in global climate governance, affected critical sectors such as agriculture, water resources, and public health, and posed a serious threat to national food security. Nonetheless, the absence of a comprehensive national climate change action plan in the period before 2001 reflected a broader lack of political will and strategic prioritisation.

This neglect was underscored by the observation of Thomas C. Schelling (2002), cited in Michael Byron Nelson's *Africa's Regional Powers and Climate Change Negotiations* (2016), who remarked:

“There is no likelihood that ... Nigeria will fully participate in any greenhouse-gas regime for the next few decades. They have done their best to make that point clear, and it serves no purpose to disbelieve them” (Nelson, M. B., 2016)

Against the backdrop of prolonged climate governance inaction, this paper seeks to investigate the impacts of climate change on Nigeria and critically examine the country's national policy responses between 2012 and 2022, a period marked by growing domestic recognition of the country's climate vulnerability and the need for structured, strategic climate governance.

Literature Review

This paper adopts an interdisciplinary methodology, making it essential to define the key concepts used in the study. Additionally, the Multiple Streams Framework is employed as the theoretical framework to guide the policy analysis.

Climate Change

Climate change as a concept has been defined and given various meanings and understandings across the board by scientists, climatologists, policymakers, etc. While the concept has been shaped to identify with the intent of the definer, the term climate change has not been inexhaustible. Onah, N. G., et al. (2016), in their work, agree with the scientific definition given by The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), that climate change is the long-term shift in global or regional weather patterns, usually as a result of increased concentrations of greenhouse gases in the Earth's atmosphere. The United Nations (2021) observed that the change in the earth's average temperature, weather, and climate patterns is largely attributed to human activities, which is termed “Anthropogenic Change”, particularly the emission of greenhouse gases (GHGs), into the atmosphere through the burning of fossil fuels.

This claim has been supported by various research, that shows that greenhouse gases (GHGs), such as carbon dioxide, methane, and water vapor, cause global warming by

trapping heat from the sun within the earth's atmosphere and cause the earth's temperature to warm up at a rapid speed, creating a distortion to the weather pattern and leading to a wide range of effects that includes melting of Iceberg, rising of sea levels, more frequent and severe weather events (flooding, heat waves, and drought), changes in precipitation patterns, and drastic change in the ecosystems and wildlife habitats (Cook, J., et al., 2016; IPCC.,2019; United Nations, 2021).

However, the burning of fossil fuels is not the only emitter of greenhouse gases, as these gases are also emitted into the atmosphere through deforestation and agricultural activities. According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) 2014 Report, Agriculture, forestry, and other land use contributed 24% of the global greenhouse gas emissions, which is a significant contribution. Trees absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere through photosynthesis and store it in their biomass and the soil. When forests are cut down or burned, their stored carbon is then released back into the atmosphere as carbon dioxide, while animals such as cattle release methane, contributing to the increase in greenhouse gases and the warming of the planet (Lothian, S. (ed.),2018).

Deforestation reduces the Earth's ability to absorb carbon dioxide because, as trees are removed, there are fewer trees available to absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, which can lead to a further increase in greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere. More so, it is pertinent to note that deforestation exacerbates other environmental problems, such as soil erosion, loss of biodiversity, and changes in local weather patterns (FAO et al., 2021).

National Development

Lawal, T., & Oluwatoyin, A. (2011). National development is a long-term, sustained effort targeted at improving the economic, social, and political well-being of a country and its citizens. Adenle, A. A., et al. (2019) noted that national development can involve a wide range of government efforts at improving infrastructure, promoting economic growth, reducing poverty and inequality, expanding access to education and healthcare, protecting the environment, and ensuring political stability and good governance. Pritchett, L. (2021) argues that national development must encompass several key features: effective administration, government responsiveness, a productive economy, and a shared national identity. He emphasises that national development is not merely a theoretical ideal but an empirical necessity for ensuring the well-being of a country's citizens. At the core of Pritchett's argument is the assertion that human well-being should be the central priority of development efforts, guiding both policy formulation and implementation.

National development, therefore, can be described as the overall development or collective socio-economic, political, and religious advancement of a country or nation, which promotes not just infrastructural development but the well-being of the citizenry. This is best achieved through strategic planning, which can be described as the country's collection of strategies mapped out by the government. However, because achieving national development requires a sustained effort, the vulnerability of a country to climate change and the impact that it has on the economic, social, and political landscape can derail existing efforts or planned actions. Hence, due to the far-

reaching effects of climate change, nations must give special attention to how to develop adaptation and mitigation plans that can help spur national development and growth (Adenle, A. A., et al., 2019).

Empirical Review

Onuoha (2009) analyses climate change as a growing global threat, with sharper impacts in developing countries where agriculture remains highly dependent on weather and climate conditions. Focusing on Nigeria, the study applies a sustainable development framework through the Great Green Wall Sahara Nigeria Programme as a response to drought and desertification in the northern region. Onuoha argues that climate change poses direct risks to economic growth and sustainable development and concludes that effective responses require integrated thinking, policy coordination, innovative approaches, and the active participation of multiple stakeholders.

Ogbuabor and Egwuchukwu (2017) examine the relationship between climate change and economic growth in Nigeria. Their findings show that carbon emissions negatively affect economic growth in both the short and long run. They link this outcome to the impact of emissions on rainfall patterns, which in turn disrupts agricultural productivity. The authors also observe that climate change contributes to forest depletion through erosion and strong winds, reducing forest products such as timber and cane. This decline affects income levels and raises the cost of construction and furniture materials. They conclude that addressing climate change impacts requires policies aimed at reducing carbon emissions and forest depletion, with implementation involving all levels of government.

Similarly, Odjugo (2005) assesses the socio-economic effects of climate change in Nigeria and finds that climate variability places disproportionate pressure on low-income and marginalised populations. The study argues that climate change deepens vulnerability by undermining livelihoods, assets, and economic stability, while increasing exposure to environmental risks. Odjugo concludes that these effects complicate poverty reduction efforts and widen existing social inequalities.

From a governance and policy perspective, Bawa-Bwari (n.d.), in a presentation to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), highlights Nigeria's institutional readiness to advance its National Adaptation Plan (NAP). She explains that the NAP process aims to strengthen adaptation capacity at federal, state, and local levels while integrating climate change into existing and future policies, plans, and development strategies. The NAP framework identifies five expected outcomes intended to prioritise adaptation, improve inter-sectoral coordination, and support long-term resilience planning within Nigeria's climate governance structure.

Albert and Baribefe-Koate (2022) examine Nigeria's National Policy on Climate Change as a policy instrument for environmental sustainability. They argue that climate change has shifted from a contested issue to a recognised global risk, leading to its inclusion among the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. According to the authors, the policy seeks to promote a low-carbon development pathway while strengthening societal resilience to climate impacts. They conclude that effective implementation of the policy could support coordination in development planning, financing, and monitoring of climate-related programmes in Nigeria.

Gap in the literature

The reviewed literature focuses largely on impacts on agriculture, economic growth, poverty, and environmental degradation (Odjugo, 2005; Onuoha, 2009; Ogbuabor & Egwuchukwu, 2017). More recent works examine national climate policies and adaptation planning as governance tools for sustainable development (Bawa-Bwari, n.d.; Albert & Baribefe-Koate, 2022). While these studies provide valuable insights into climate impacts and policy intentions, they pay limited attention to how climate policies emerge, gain political attention, and are sustained over time.

Specifically, the literature rarely examines climate governance in Nigeria through a policy process lens that explains change and continuity across political administrations. There is little analysis of how climate-related problems are framed, how policy solutions are generated and selected, and how political conditions shape policy adoption. As a result, existing research tends to describe policy outcomes rather than explain why certain climate policies advance while others stagnate or fail.

Theoretical Framework

This paper finds the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) suitable for analysing Nigeria's climate policy responses between 2012 and 2022. Originally developed by John Kingdon, the MSF provides a non-linear and interpretive approach to understanding how policies emerge, why some issues gain political attention, and why others are neglected (Knaggård, Å., 2015; Herweg, N. et al., 2018). The framework conceptualises the policy process as comprising three largely independent streams: the problem stream, which identifies and frames issues requiring governmental attention; the policy stream, which consists of ideas, proposals, and solutions developed by experts and analysts; and the politics stream, which includes political events, public opinion, national mood, and changes in leadership or ideology.

The Multiple Stream Framework (MSF) emphasises that when these three streams converge, they open a policy window, an opportunity for significant policy change (e.g., a change in administration), the problem stream (e.g., a major climate disaster), or both. The MSF also bring into bear the important role of the policy entrepreneur (individuals, organisations, or institutions) that invest time, resources, and expertise to match problems with solutions and advocate for their adoption at opportune moments. Policy entrepreneurs are crucial in seizing the opportunity presented by a policy window, persuading decision-makers to place specific issues on the political agenda. If unsuccessful, they may repurpose their proposals for future opportunities or adapt them to different contexts.

By applying the MSF, this paper is able to identify which elements of the policy process were effectively aligned in Nigeria's climate response vis-à-vis national development and where disjunctures occurred, thereby explaining the success or failure of various climate initiatives within the decade under review.

1.2. Research Methods

This study adopts a qualitative, interpretive methodology grounded in contextual analysis. Using purposive sampling, the study relies on selected secondary sources that focus on climate governance in Nigeria and the country's responses to climate change. The analysis examines how Nigeria's climate governance frameworks, policies, and institutional arrangements have evolved and how they align with global climate norms and international commitments.

1.3. Results and Discussion

Climate change and its impact in Nigeria

Since independence, the country has grappled with the issues of national development, and the successive governments have adopted various plans and strategies that have failed to yield significant results, as a large number of the country's population still lives below the poverty line. The impact of climate change has become prevalent in key sectors such as agriculture, water resources, energy, health, and infrastructure, which form the crop of the country's national development. Slow national development threatens human well-being. In recent years, Nigeria has made some socio-economic progress in recent years, but its human capital development remains low, largely due to under-investment in that sector; the country ranked 158 of 189 countries in the World Bank's 2019 Human Capital Index (Nelson, M. B., 2016).

The impact of climate change across various regions of the country poses a significant threat to human well-being. Some regions are more prone to climate impact than others, especially as it relates to their climate resilience. When communities lack the ability to absorb climate shock, they are more vulnerable to impact from climate crises, and the most affected sector in Nigeria for climate change is the agricultural sector, that form the bloodstream of local communities. Climate shocks experienced in local communities are transmuted directly and indirectly to big towns and cities in various forms (Birkmann, J. et al., 2022).

The 2012 nationwide flooding brought to the forefront the cascading damage which climate change causes to national development. It further shows that Nigeria, just like every other country, is susceptible to the impact of climate change. Various studies have shown that climate change has the potential to exacerbate existing economic and political stresses, especially when nations are not prepared to absorb climate shock (Ojonigu, F. A. et al., 2018). According to the 2021 Notre Dame Global Adaptation Index, Nigeria is ranked the 53rd most vulnerable country and the 6th least prepared country in the world to cope with climate change (Nwankpa, A., 2022).

In the northern part of the country, climate change-induced dry spells, drought, desertification, and heatwaves, aggravated by overgrazing and unsustainable land practices, are causing land degradation, rising health risks such as recurrent meningitis outbreaks, and increasing poverty levels among rural populations. Declining rainfall and prolonged dry spells contributed to the drying up of water bodies and the loss of grazing lands, triggering internal migration with herders and rain-fed farmers moving southward in search of arable land and water resources. This migration intensified

competition over land and water, fueling farmer–herder conflicts and straining intercommunal relations.

EM-DAT report shows that the 2022 drought affected 19.1 million people in Nigeria, and it contributed significantly to herder’s migration down south of the country, resulting in farmers' and herders' clashes, and fewer water supplies for use in agriculture, hydro power generation, and other uses (CRED.,2022; Ogbuabor, J. E., & Egwuchukwu, E. I., 2017). Lack of local resilience and adaptation mechanisms, especially at the local community level, has led to an increase in conflicts over land resources for farming and grazing. The violence between farmers and herders has worsened over the past decade and has disrupted food production, contributing significantly to food insecurity.

In recent years, climate-induced conflict between farmers and herders in states like Adamawa, Jos, Kogi, Kaduna, and Benue has resulted in numerous tragic incidents, causing loss of lives and displacement of residents. One such incident occurred on May 16, 2017, where twenty lives were lost in a clash between farmers and herders in Yola South Local Government Area. Similarly, in November 2019, several communities in Bangshika ward of Hong Local Government Area were affected by a conflict between herdsman and farmers, resulting in the displacement of thousands of individuals and causing casualties (The Kukah Centre,2018).

In some parts of the country, climate change manifested in the form of weather variability such as irregular rainfall patterns, recurrent flooding, and heatwaves, all of which disrupted agricultural production, displaced communities, and destabilised local economies. In 2022 alone, the country recorded 603 deaths and a staggering economic loss of US\$4.2 billion due to flooding (CRED.,2022). Previous reports indicate that between 2002 and 2021, Nigeria had the highest number of people affected by floods in Africa, with 11,419,911 people directly impacted, resulting in 1,551 deaths. In the northern part of the country, drought is gaining significant ground, and the alarm bells are ringing with lakes drying up and a reduction in river flow in the arid and semi-arid region (UNICEF., 2023).

2022 Flooding in Lokoja, Kogi State

Incidence of flooding across the country as a result of rising sea levels is becoming widespread. In a recent publication, it has been stated that Lagos state is sinking and

under threat of coastal inundation and flood, causing the spread of diseases. States of Kogi, Edo, Anambra, Delta, and Benue, etc., have in the last decade experienced an increase in flooding that affects agricultural, economic, and social activities (Adelekan, I. O., 2010).

Nigeria's agricultural sector is already facing severe challenges due to the changing climate, unpredictable rainfall patterns, droughts, and floods. The agricultural sector suffers the largest impact of climate change because it is a climate-sensitive sector (Kelechi, J. A., et al., 2022). Studies also show that agriculture, which is highly susceptible to climate change, forms a major economic sustenance for a larger population of the country (Ughaelu, C. M., 2017). The agro-sector directly or indirectly employs 70 per cent of the country's labour force and contributes immensely to its national development (Akingba, O. O., et al., 2022). The 22.35% contribution of the agro-sector to the overall GDP in the first Quarter of 2021 shows the importance of the sector (Ani, K. J., et al., 2022). The effect of climate change on the agricultural sector in Nigeria poses a threat to national development because about 70% of the labour force in the country works along the agro-sector value chain (Ani, K. J., et al., 2022). The consistent alterations in climatic patterns have continuously exerted adverse effects on agricultural productivity in Nigeria, leading to instability and unsustainability in food production (Ani, K. J., et al., 2022).

In the northern part of the country, climate-induced drought and desertification have caused farmlands to be abandoned (Idumah, F. O., et al., 2016). Yusufari, a town in Yobe state, has been impacted by a climate-induced drought and desertification, causing residents to abandon the once-bustling town. Satellite data shows that between 2012 and 2022, the following villages in Yobe state, such as Faragaa, Gafade, Garshelek, Kilboa, Ndijiu, Njikilamma, Sadan, and Sakaa, have experienced even more severe consequences (Adebajo, K., & Abdullahi, M., 2022)

Rising temperatures and heatwaves have adverse health consequences, such as cerebrospinal meningitis, cardiovascular and respiratory disorders in elderly individuals, skin cancer, high blood pressure, malaria, cholera, and child and maternal health issues. In northern Nigeria, the incidence of meningitis has been on the rise due to excessive heat (Ilevbare, 2020). While in the south, changes in temperature, rainfall patterns and flooding have given rise to the frequency of outbreaks and spread of diseases such as malaria, cholera and dengue fever.

Some of the visible evidence of climate-induced catastrophe, such as flooding are on infrastructure. Rising waters and flooding not only cause forced migration, but causes damages worth millions of dollars on infrastructures. According to a report by the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development (FMHADMSD), after the post-disaster assessment on the 2022 flooding, the total direct economic damage was estimated at \$6.68 bn (Ani, K. J., et al., 2022).

According to the U.N. High Commissioner for Refugees, climate-related disasters force an average of 21.5 million people from their homes around the world. This number is expected to rise due to rising seas, drought, searing temperatures, and other climate catastrophes (Watson, J., 2022). These climate-induced shocks directly and indirectly affect sustained national development, as well as food, cultural and traditional

practices, which are tied to seasonal weather cycles and the environment. Compounding these climate-induced pressures are anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, oil spills, mining, and overgrazing, which have accelerated ecosystem degradation and amplified the vulnerability among rural populations. The combined effect of these factors has entrenched environmental injustice, deepened gender inequalities, and widened class disparities, as marginalised communities often bear the brunt of climate impacts while lacking access to adaptation resources and decision-making platforms.

Nigeria's Climate Policy Response through the Lens of the Multiple Streams Framework

When analysed through the lens of the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) of policy analysis, Nigeria's response to climate change emerges as the outcome of several interrelated factors. These include the country's active participation in international climate agreements, its economic dependence on fossil fuels as a primary source of foreign revenue, the advocacy of civil society and non-governmental organisations both within and outside its borders, as well as the influence of the media, academia, local stakeholders, and the broader governance architecture.

Collectively, these actors play a significant role in shaping Nigeria's climate policy response, which in turn has critical implications for national development and economic growth. According to the 2021 Notre Dame Global Adaptation Index, Nigeria ranks as the 53rd most vulnerable country to climate change globally, and the 6th least prepared to cope with its impacts. This stark ranking highlights a considerable gap between policy formulation and effective implementation.

The increasing severity of climate-induced challenges, exacerbated by anthropogenic activities such as oil spills, mining, deforestation, and land degradation, forms the core of the problem stream in the MSF, opening up windows of opportunities for policy entrepreneurs. These environmental challenges have both direct and indirect impacts on Nigeria's socio-economic landscape, particularly undermining the agricultural sector.

Among the most affected sectors, agriculture stands out due to its high sensitivity to climate variability. The devastating floods of 2012 and 2022, for instance, destroyed vast swathes of farmland across the country, leading to significant financial losses and reductions in food production (Umar, N., & Grey, A., 2023). In the northern regions, advancing desertification and prolonged droughts are reducing arable land, especially for farmers who are dependent on rain-fed agriculture. These cascading crises have contributed to internal displacement, intensified herder-farmer conflicts, deepened poverty, and exacerbated existing gender inequalities, collectively necessitating the urgent need for a more coordinated and effective climate response (Duruji, M. M., & Bella, F., 2024; The Kukah Centre, 2018; Olaniyan, A., & Okeke-Uzodike, U., 2015; Odoh, S. I., & Chilaka, F. C., 2012)

Nigeria's climate policy has been notably shaped by its alignment with international, regional, and sub-regional climate frameworks, which shows that external actors play a key role within the policy stream and Politics stream. The country's commitments to the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Agreement, the Kigali Amendment to the Montreal

Protocol, the Great Green Wall Initiative, and the ECOWAS Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policies have all influenced the country's policy direction (Adigwe, A. N., 2024; Ogah, A., 2021, FME.,2021; United Nation.,2015; Burns, W. C. G., & Osofsky, H. M., 2009). These frameworks have not only provided a foundation for domestic climate policy development but have also created critical policy windows within the political stream. Through these commitments, Nigeria has gained access to financial and technical resources, while also enhancing its legitimacy on the global stage.

Public awareness and advocacy around climate change have steadily increased, driven by the efforts of media, civil society organisations, climate activists, academia, and international development partners. As a result, climate policy formulation and implementation in Nigeria now occur within a complex, multi-layered governance structure involving a wide range of stakeholders at both national and sub-national levels.

However, a retrospective analysis of Nigeria's post-1999 democratic era reveals a delayed governmental response to climate change, despite growing evidence of its impacts. This inertia can be partly attributed to economic concerns, particularly fears that a transition away from fossil fuel exports would undermine national revenue. Additionally, some policymakers viewed climate change discourse as a geopolitical tool or "propaganda" advanced by the Global North to curb the economic growth of developing nations.

Nigeria's evolving response to climate change reflects the dynamic interaction among problem recognition, policy solutions, and political will—core elements of the MSF. While recent developments suggest an increasing commitment to addressing climate change, significant challenges remain in aligning short-term economic interests with long-term sustainability and resilience goals.

Some Key Indicators of Nigeria's Response to Climate Change between 2012 and 2022

Between 2012 and 2022, Nigeria's response to climate change evolved from fragmented, reactive measures to more structured and institutionalised policies. The country made significant strides in strengthening its legal and policy frameworks in response to climate change. The country not only improved its legislative mechanisms but also adopted a range of strategic policies aimed at promoting renewable energy adoption, efforts that aligned with international climate commitments under the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement, and are targeted at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, minimising dependence on fossil fuels, and promoting sustainable and clean living.

The 2012 nationwide flooding, which displaced millions and caused widespread infrastructural damage, served as a critical turning point that highlighted the country's vulnerability to climate-induced disasters (Umar, N., & Grey, A., 2023). In response, Nigeria adopted the National Policy on Climate Change (NPCC) in 2012 and established the Department of Climate Change (DCC) within the Federal Ministry of Environment to coordinate climate-related actions (FME.,2012). The ratification of the Paris Agreement in 2017 further signified Nigeria's international commitment to mitigation, with the country pledging to cut emissions by 20% unconditionally and 45% conditionally by 2030 through its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).

A significant milestone occurred with the enactment of the Climate Change Act in 2021, which created the National Council on Climate Change (NCCC) and provided a legal framework for achieving a net-zero target by 2060. After the 2012 flooding, Nigeria's climate change policy response to food production evolved from a reactive to a strategic one. The cornerstone of Nigeria's formal response was the approval of the National Climate Change Policy and Response Strategy (NCCPRS) in 2012. Although a strategy document, this framework is targeted at climate-smart agriculture and food security. It supported research into climate-smart agriculture (CSA) techniques, improving weather forecasting and early warning systems for farmers, while also promoting the development and dissemination of drought- and flood-resistant crop and livestock varieties. This was further boosted with initiatives such as the Agricultural Promotion Policy (2016-2020). Also, programs such as the Great Green Wall were aimed at combating desertification in the north.

The landmark Climate Change Act of 2021 provided a legislative backbone for climate action, while also creating a framework for accessing international climate finance (e.g., Green Climate Fund) that can be channelled into large-scale climate-resilient agricultural projects. Complementing this was the launch of Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan (ETP) in 2022, which laid out a strategy for expanding renewable energy, promoting green jobs, and reducing dependence on fossil fuels.

Another key area where there is infrastructural development as a key indicator for Nigeria's climate policy response is within the energy sector. Between 2012 and 2022, Nigeria invested heavily in the energy sector, both in infrastructural development and policies targeted. In 2013, Nigeria updated its Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP), which set ambitious targets of achieving 23% renewable energy share by 2025 and 36% by 2030. In 2015, the government introduced two pivotal frameworks: the NERC Renewable Energy Feed-In Tariff (REFiT) and the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP). These policies were designed to attract private sector investment by offering guaranteed tariffs, ensuring grid access for renewable producers, and fostering a diverse energy mix that includes solar, wind, biomass, and small hydro sources.

The NREEEP, in particular, provided a national framework for scaling renewable energy and improving energy efficiency. Its objectives included: reducing greenhouse gas emissions in line with Nigeria's climate obligations; encouraging energy sustainability in households, industry, and transport; lowering energy costs, especially in rural and underserved areas; creating green jobs; stimulating economic growth; and promoting technology transfer. Importantly, the policy also outlined legal and institutional mechanisms for capacity building and financing renewable energy projects.

In the same year, the REFiT policy established fixed tariffs and guaranteed grid access to support renewable energy investments. This made Nigeria's energy sector more attractive to private investors and aligned clean energy development with national development and climate resilience strategies. Further progress came with the Mini-Grid Regulation (2016), which facilitated decentralised energy access, particularly in rural areas. Then, in 2021, the Value Added Tax (VAT) (Modification) Order explicitly exempted renewable energy equipment from VAT, making the importation and distribution of these technologies more cost-effective.

According to the Climatescope 2024 report, clean energy investment in Nigeria peaked at \$279.7 million in 2021, although it dropped significantly to \$21.96 million in 2022. However, by 2024, Nigeria had emerged as one of the top 10 markets globally for renewable energy investment, a notable rise from its rankings of 32nd in 2023 and 16th in 2022. This rapid improvement is largely attributed to initiatives such as the Solar Power Naija Project, which provided over ₦140 billion (approximately US\$340 million) in loans under the Economic Sustainability Plan (ESP) to accelerate solar electrification across Nigeria, as well other key investment in the energy sector such as the World Bank and AfDB funding of US \$350 million and US \$148 million respectively for the Nigeria Electrification Programme, project like the revamping of the 10 MW Katsina Wind Farm which was initially started in 2005, and \$2.2 billion signed in 2023 for 961 MW solar plus battery storage, and various other showed commitment.

Despite these advancements, Nigeria's climate response remained hampered by challenges such as limited implementation capacity, inadequate funding, political delays, and continued economic reliance on oil. Nonetheless, increasing public awareness, civil society activism, and engagement with international partners indicate a growing momentum toward climate resilience and sustainable development.

1.4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Nigeria's climate change policy responses since 2012 have been influenced by a combination of factors and actors. The Country's vulnerability to the impact of climate change has driven the need to have cohesive policies, cross-sectoral collaboration, and global cooperation to address the intricate relationship between climate change and national development. Nigeria, with its large population and reliance on climate-sensitive sectors like agriculture and natural resources, is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Despite emitting only 0.36% of the world's greenhouse gas emissions, Nigeria is already experiencing adverse climate conditions affecting the welfare of millions of people and posing a threat to national development.

An analysis through the Multiple Streams Framework reveals that Nigeria's climate policy response from 2012 to 2022 was characterised by significant institutional and legislative advancement shaped by the problem stream, yet persistently undermined by a critical implementation gap. The convergence of the problem stream, which manifested in climate-induced agricultural devastation, flooding, displacement, food insecurity and rising farmers-herder clashes, with a well-developed policy stream of international and domestic frameworks, successfully opened policy windows for landmark actions such as the Climate Change Act (2021).

However, the politics stream, which remained dominated by the countervailing force of economic dependence on fossil fuels and compounded by weak sub-national capacity and inadequate financing, has consistently impeded the translation of ambitious policy into tangible resilience and climate actions. Consequently, Nigeria remains highly vulnerable, with its agricultural sector acutely exposed to climatic shocks.

To bridge this gap, this study thus recommends that the Nigerian government should prioritise the full operationalisation of the Climate Change Act, empowering the National Council on Climate Change to enforce cross-sectoral compliance and develop concrete localised adaptation models. Furthermore, policy efforts must be directed toward deconstructing the political economy of fossil fuel reliance by strategically leveraging revenues from the energy sector to fund a robust national climate fund accessible from the local government level. This fund should explicitly finance scalable climate-smart agriculture initiatives, decentralised renewable energy projects, and capacity-building at the sub-national level to ensure that policy coherence is achieved from the national to the local arena, thereby aligning short-term economic interests with long-term sustainable development goals.

1.5. References

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